

Welcome to SoldAC First Newsletter!

SoldAC designs a system to convert CO₂ into ethylene

Welcome to the first newsletter of the European project SoldAC. The project focuses on researching and designing a new system to convert CO₂ into ethylene. It has already been nine months since SoldAC started working on developing a photoelectrochemical conversion unit which exploits bandwidth-selected light from a solar collector that splits the solar spectrum for electricity and heat generation at an efficiency higher than standalone photovoltaic modules and standalone solar thermal collectors, and the heat generated is used in an innovative direct air capture unit that removes CO₂ from the air. COMET leads the consortium formed by LOMARTOV, IREC-CERCA, CNR, UDL, EIM, UEDIN and USTAN, to face the challenge of developing this new system to produce carbon-neutral ethylene and byproduct ethanol from the air in an independent off-grid and market-competitive process powered by solar energy.

In 36 months, SoldAC will bring the materials, the engineering and the technology provided by each partner to University of Lleida lab. The consortium will develop the validation lab infrastructure, integrate all components and test the whole SoldAC system, including infrastructure for solar light harvesting, cold light provision, and thermal energy production and storage. The project, funded by the European Commission (GA 101069359) and Innovate UK (ISF 10039331-10038044), will invest 3M€ to design this new system to convert CO₂ into ethylene.

You are invited to subscribe to our newsletter to keep updated about SoldAC's achievements towards reinventing the ethylene industry by providing an emerging breakthrough technology for producing technically and economically competitive and climate-neutral sustainable ethylene and co-product ethanol from solar energy and air.

(1) COMET, (2) LOMARTOV, (3) IREC-CERCA, (4) CNR, (5) UDL, (6) EIM, (7) UEDIN, (8) USTAN

- Full name: Full Spectrum Solar Direct Air Capture and Conversion
- Acronym: SoldAC
- Number of partners: 8
- Start date: 1 September 2022
- Duration: 36 months
- Total budget: 3 M €
- EC funding: 2 M €
- UKRI funding: 1 M €
- Partners acronyms: COMET, LOMARTOV, IREC-CERCA, CNR, UDL, EIM, UEDIN, USTAN

Check out the website: www.soldac-project.eu

At the SoldAC website, you can find all the information about the project.

- Objectives & Impacts
- Lab testing
- Consortium
- News & Events
- Publications & Results

CO₂ Storage and Capture Conference in Barcelona

IREC participates in the conference held in Barcelona and organized by APIA and PTECO2. It included 5 talks covering aspects of the CO₂ cycle: from fossil fuels combustion to capture, utilization and storage together with socio-economical aspects and current projects in the UE and Spain related with CCUS technologies.

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UEDIN Gives the Keynote Speech During the Webinar "Engineering and Material Challenges in Atmospheric Carbon Capture, Storage and Utilization"

UEDIN, one of the SoldAC project partners, meets the University of Technology and Applied Sciences (UTAS), one of the most lively and fast-growing higher education institutions in Oman.

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First General Assembly in Barcelona

The first General Assembly was held at the UPC Campus Diagonal Besòs facilities and was hosted by IREC-CERCA. It was a great opportunity to meet again and exchange knowledge of the different units that are part of the overall system.

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Successful Kick Off Meeting in Barcelona

The SoldAC project kick off meeting was held in Barcelona in September 2022 to start discussing and developing the prototype that will reduce carbon footprint through the capture and direct conversion of CO₂ from the atmosphere.

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Meet Our Partners

USTAN Interview

Paul A. Wright
University of St Andrews

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UEDIN Interview

Giulio Santori
The University of Edinburgh

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CNR Interview

Valeria Palomba
CNR

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Past events

Sustainable Technology Forum in Valencia in March 2023

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Solar2Chem Winter School in Valencia in February 2023

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Upcoming events

Heat Powered Cycles (Edinburgh, 3rd-6th September)

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First SoldAC Workshop (Edinburgh, 5th September)

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